

COLOSTRUM FEEDING: THE SCIENCE AND ART OF SAFEGUARDING NEWBORN CALVES FROM ILLNESSES

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ABSTRACT

The success of dairy cattle rearing depends on methods that enhance the health and growth efficiency of neonates, which in turn affect replacement rates and the financial viability of dairy production systems. Ensuring adequate colostrum intake with a minimum of 50 mg IgG/mL is vital to prevent FPT and safeguard the calf's health. Colostrum feeding is an example of early-life nutrition that can significantly affect calf's overall performance, including average daily gain (ADG), health status, and survival rates.

Keywords: gut closure, passive immunity, immunoglobulins

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